

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE FORMATION OF SPEECH CULTURE IN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract: The integration of subjects and fields in language education develops the ability to use the language in practice. In order to strengthen the practical aspect of grammar knowledge, texts on various topics are referred to. In this, the process of connection between language science and various disciplines and fields occurs. The article contains some recommendations for primary class pupils (college and lyceum) and independent learners of foreign languages.

Key words: language education, integration, interdisciplinary integration, interdisciplinary communication, speech culture, foreign language, comparative linguistics. Integration in education is the process of establishing connections between the components of the content within a certain educational system in order to form a holistic view of the world aimed at the development of the student's personality and self-development. Integratsiya (lat. integratio - restore, start again, complete) 1. The concept that expresses the state of dependence of some names, elements, and their integration. 2. It is a process of interrelation of sciences, which is important to every learner who is learning a foreign language in the process of language learning. Abu Nasr Farabi (great uzbek scholar) states that "Words are of four types: the first are words that do not need to be known and said; the second is words that are necessary to know and say, and the third is words that do not need to be known, but can be said; the fourth is the words that can be known, but do not need to be said... I have explained these four words. The best of these are the words that need to be known and spoken." Learning a language requires meaningful expressions to express one's thoughts. Language needs thoughts as well as thoughts.

Today, our education system cannot be imagined without the process of integration. Integration means "whole", so it is the integration of different parts and elements of the process of thinking growth into a single whole. This shows interdisciplinarity in education, teaching subjects in close connection with each other. Integration of subjects in modern education is one of the ways of developing the creative potential of pedagogical staff to actively search for new pedagogical solutions, to have an effective and reasonable impact on students. Interdisciplinary integration in education also ensures that students acquire a set of universal values while studying other disciplines and fields in an interconnected and related manner.

Pupils will thoroughly and deeply understand the essence of educational materials, the laws of nature and society's development on a scientific basis. All topics taught in learning English (and other foreign languages) are based on the study of language phenomena in connection with various disciplines and fields. That is, texts on different topics are recommended. In the process of language learning, since the information (in the texts) related

to science or fields unrelated to language science consists of a set of knowledge, the concepts necessary in social life, the process of inter-science or field integration occurs. Knowing is done through thought and language. The materialization of thinking is carried out through speech. It is necessary to be able to choose the appropriate language units (lexical, grammatical means) for the speech situation. A complex requirement for language education is students' speech culture development. Speech culture includes both everyday (free) communication and how to speak in different situations. Each lesson should be aimed at developing speech culture. For this, in the lesson processes (before starting), wise words, proverbs, poems (can be a stanza, even a verse) or sentences from works of art, short fragments, instead of humor (Because the incident taken under laughter- at the heart of events is a lesson.) use serves to strengthen the student's knowledge of language science, to receive education along with education, and, most importantly, to develop his thinking. Good mastery of grammatical knowledge and language norms allows for accurate, clear and fluent expression of thought, and this leads to the improvement of speech culture and methodology will be the basis.

Education, spirituality, literacy of each person is measured by his words and speech. A person's inner world, humaneness, honesty, and culture in general are revealed through speech. Although oral and written communication are related to each other, they also have their own characteristics. Spoken speech is pronounced and heard. In this, a person uses tone, pauses and various non-verbal means to express his thoughts. The ability to use these tools correctly should be formed in students. Literacy is required in written speech. When a person expresses his thoughts in writing, he receives information from others through the organs of vision and hearing and expresses his attitude. The advantage of written speech is that when describing the expressed event, concept, etc. in words, if a word, phrase or adverb is used incorrectly, they can be replaced with another suitable option. possible But there is no such opportunity in oral speech, so the thought to be expressed should be thought through in every way and then expressed. In T learning stages, topics progress from simple to complex. For example, in English language classes, students should know the language features and styles of literary texts, thus, one of the types of work performed in the development of their speech culture is to identify and interpret a language phenomenon or style from it, and to be able to distinguish speech styles from each other. For this, the teacher is required to impart theoretical knowledge and create sufficient skills and competencies in students to be able to apply them in practice. At first, the teacher gives general information about speech styles and writes down the necessary resources for the students. After the statement of the new topic, the teacher directly connects the topic with other subjects. For this, the teacher distributes handouts with different types of texts to the students. With this, the teacher makes the lesson interesting and at the same time allows the student to be active. For example, we can use the following materials:

Passage 1: A so-called 'smile of respect' is seen as insincere and often regarded with suspicion in Russia. A famous Russian proverb even states that 'laughing without reason is a sign of idiocy'. Yet in countries like the United States, Australia and Britain, smiling is often interpreted as a sign of openness, friendship and respect.

Passage 2: An American or British person might be looking their client in the eye to show that they are paying full attention to what is being said, but if that client is from Japan or Korea, they might find the direct eye contact awkward or even disrespectful. In parts of South America and Africa, prolonged eye contact could also be seen as challenging authority. In the Middle East, eye contact across genders is considered inappropriate, although eye contact within a gender could signify honesty and truthfulness.

Therefore, in language lessons, grammatical rules are studied in connection with the development of speech. The beginning of learning about syntax serves as a basis for the development of speaking skills. Phrase and sentence tone, pronunciation of the sentence with a complete tone, logical (logical) stress, tone of speech of the secondary clauses together with the main clauses, intonation, pause should be followed:

"There once was a poor shepherd boy who used to watch his flocks in the fields next to a dark forest near the foot of a mountain. One hot afternoon, he thought up a good plan to get some company for himself and also have a little fun. Raising his fist in the air, he ran down to the village shouting "Wolf, Wolf." As soon as they heard him, the villagers all rushed from their homes, full of concern for his safety, and two of his cousins even stayed with him for a short while"

As English serves the purpose of international communication, most of the foreign language learners try to learn it. In this process, they have to acquire all the four basic skills of the language listening, speaking, reading and writing.

English is the language widely used in the field of scientific research, education, business, the internet, travel and tourism, media and newspapers, software, medicine, engineering, information and technology, entertainment, banking and so on.

In conclusion, if the phonetic method is taught to the student or students in the language learning classes, the word stress, syntagm stress, and pause in oral speech or texts should be correctly placed. winter sleep increases cognitive efficiency. The use of video, audio texts, information from social networks and other texts recommended in the lesson effectively affects the development of speech culture skills along with language learning. Based on the content of the texts, integration of disciplines, interdisciplinary use of the studied language materials in practice forms skills and competencies.

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